

POLYMER DYNAMICS APPLIED TO PEEK MATRIX COMPOSITES WELDING

Jean-Florent Lamèthe and Pierre Beauchêne
Office National d'Etudes et de Recherches Aérospatiales (ONERA)
Département Matériaux et Systèmes Composites
29, avenue de la Division Leclerc BP 72
92 322 Châtillon cedex, France

Liliane Léger
Laboratoire de Physique des Fluides Organisés, UMR CNRS 7125
Collège de France
11, place Marcellin Berthelot
75 231 Paris cedex 05, France

SUMMARY: Continuous composite processes such as thermoplastic automated tow placement are based on fusion bonding or healing of thermoplastic matrix. A good understanding of interdiffusion and crystallization, the main phenomena at the interface, is important. Self-bonding was studied first in PEEK (Poly-ether-ether-ketone) and then in the same matrix reinforced by carbon fibers. This leads to the development of a macroscopic method for analyzing interdiffusion, that predicts the mode I critical strain energy release rate as function of processing conditions. A new experimental device was developed in order to prepare short-time welded samples which were mechanically characterized using a wedge double beam cantilever test. The thermal modeling explains the importance of the interface cooling curve for interdiffusion.

KEYWORDS: adhesion, bonding, PEEK, welding, interdiffusion, reptation

INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials is increasing due to the weight saving compared to metallic parts with equivalent function. Much research is underway on these materials, especially on continuous processing methods using the thermoplastic fusibility properties. The aeronautic industry is particularly interested in thermoplastic automated tow placement applied to PEEK carbon fiber reinforced composites for manufacturing structural parts [1 and references included]. The quality of the final part is thus controlled by the fusion bonding efficiency. This was analyzed in this work using a macroscopic method, as it is very difficult to get microscopic information due to the complexity of the studied prepregs. We present an experimental investigation of PEEK and PEEK carbon fiber composite welds, characterized by the wedge double cantilever beam test; a rather classical approach previously used to investigate joining of other semi-crystalline polymers [3,4]. The aim of this work is to understand the influence of the welding parameters (temperature, time and pressure) on the microscopic interdiffusion phenomenon in PEEK based systems and then predict the adhesion of welded samples from processing conditions. Interdiffusion was already demonstrated to be the dominant process leading to adhesion enhancement in amorphous polymers [5] based on the reptation picture of polymer dynamics due to de Gennes [6]. We do not include here other phenomena such as intimate contact which has been widely studied [2 and included references]. This is due to the

extremely low roughness of our samples and the improvement of the prepreg roughness. Polymer degradation is also neglected since we work over short time-scales and in the low end of the temperature range in which degradation occurs.

BACKGROUND

Adhesion is controlled by interdiffusion, in which polymer chains penetrate in both sides of the interface. Thus, polymer dynamics plays a major role in this phenomenon and it is important to have a correct model to describe it. Several models have emerged to describe chain dynamics, but the reptation theory is the most accurate as confirmed by the comparison realized by Welp [8]. Moreover, it has been validated by various experimental techniques in the case of model polymers [9-11]. We describe it briefly.

The reptation model

The model of reptation describes the local Brownian motion of a polymer chain of length L in a melt [6,7]. The entanglements with neighboring chains impose topological constraints upon the chain restricting lateral motion. Thus, the polymer chain is confined to move backward and forward along the curvilinear length of a tube and can explore new regions only by the ends. The motion of the chain within the tube is modeled as the migration of defects along the backbone. The tube size is related to the average distance between entanglements. The reptation time, which is the time necessary for the entire chain to escape from the initial tube is given as:

$$t_{rep} \propto N^3 \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of monomers in the chain.

The diffusion coefficient of a chain can be expressed as:

$$D_{rep} = \frac{kT N_e}{\zeta N} \propto N^{-2} \quad (2)$$

with ζ , the monomer friction coefficient,
 N_e , the number of monomers between entanglements,
 k , the Boltzmann constant
 T , the temperature.

Adhesion between amorphous polymers

De Gennes has modeled the welding of amorphous polymers at a microscopic scale using the reptation theory [12]. An important parameter for the calculation of the fracture energy $G_{IC}(t)$ in samples healed over a time t is the density $p(t)$ of bridges established between the two sides of the interface [13]. If the fracture occurs by chain breakage, the energy $G_{IC}(t)$ is expressed as:

$$G_{IC} \cong p^2(t) \quad (3)$$

and $G_{IC}(t) \sim t^{1/2}$ as is indeed observed [5]. For the opposite case of plastic failure, $G_{IC}(t) \sim t$.

In his minor chain model, Wool assumes that the strength of an interface is directly proportional to the interpenetration depth of the chains [14]. This could not be sufficient when describing the fracture of the interface because it does not take into account bridging effects. Nonetheless, it is quite difficult to predict the evolution of G_{IC} with the number of chains that cross the interface in the case of contact of

the same polymer. Thus, many studies have been performed with immiscible polymers using blocks or random copolymers to analyze adhesion and fracture from the molecular to the macroscopic scale [15].

Adhesion between semi-crystalline polymers

Although the interfacial properties of amorphous polymers are now quite well understood, a few studies have concentrated on semi-crystalline polymer assemblies [16-19], since their behavior is more complex. Semi-crystalline polymers are typically two-phase materials where each phase has different mechanical properties. Moreover, the microscopic mechanisms for reinforcement are more complex because there are other additional effects besides entanglement, notably co-crystallization and microstructural effects. Healing of semi-crystalline polymers was studied for polypropylene and polyamide 12 [3,4].

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The composite materials used in this study were AS4 carbon fibers reinforcing poly (ether-ether-ketone) (PEEK) thermoplastic prepreg ribbons (referred to as APC2) with a thickness of 0.150 mm, available from Cytec Fiberite. The volume fraction of the AS4 carbon fibers in APC2 was 68%. PEEK samples were also used and cut from 1 mm-thick sheets, available from Goodfellow, which transforms Victrex 450 PEEK grade. The average molecular weight, M_w is of the order of 44 000 g/mol and the polydispersity is 2.7 [20]. The radius of gyration of PEEK molecule is 18.7 nm. The roughness of both PEEK and composite materials are both less than 2 μm . The glass transition and melting temperature T_g and T_f were determined by DSC and are respectively 143°C and 345°C for PEEK samples and 149 and 351°C for APC2 sample. We can assume no degradation effect of the polymer in the temperature range we are working in, since PEEK is stable up to 450°C in air and 500°C in nitrogen [21].

Welded samples processing

Two different welding experiments were performed on both PEEK and PEEK carbon fiber reinforced composites depending on temperature and welding time.

Long time welded samples: To explore temperatures close to the melting point, two parts were joined in a mould under pressure and placed in an oven under argon controlled atmosphere to prevent oxidation, for times varying from 1h to 1000h.

Short time welded samples: A new experimental device was developed to produce, under controlled conditions (time, pressure and temperature), samples welded during shorter times at temperatures over the melting point. The principle is explained in Figure 1. The advantage of this method is that overheating only occurs at the surfaces that come into contact; this is not the case for other techniques [3,4,21]. Firstly, two parts were stuck to mounts which were preheated to a constant temperature. Then, an infrared source at 845°C (determined using a pyrometer) was swept between the two parts

for a few seconds. 1.3 seconds after the withdrawal of the IR source, pressure was applied and the two parts were brought into contact. Heating of the mounts was then cut and the sample cooled.

Figure 1: Principle of the experimental device (1) Mount preheating (2) Infrared source insertion and holding (3) Pressure applied

Adhesion characterization: the wedge test

Adhesion energy was measured using a wedge test (Figure 2), more appropriate for a quantitative evaluation than other commonly used tests such as lap shears [22]. In this test, a wedge with a known thickness is pushed between the two welded parts in order to propagate the fracture at a speed of an order of $1 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, Figure 3. The adhesion energy corresponds to the energy stored in the elastically deformed double cantilever beam and can be calculated by measuring the crack length, a . For mode I, the fracture energy release rate of the bonds is [23]:

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3 E h^3 \Delta^2}{16 a^4} \quad (4)$$

where E is the material Young modulus and h and Δ are respectively the beam and wedge thickness and a is the crack length.

Figure 2: wedge double beam cantilever test

The position of the crack tip was recorded using a video camera. Around 25 photos were taken on each sample with a millimeter interval. An example of recorded image during the wedge test is given in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Image recorded during the wedge test for a PEEK weld sample with double cantilever beam geometry

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Adhesion measurement results

The experiments performed in the oven under argon show that it was possible to weld PEEK semi-crystalline polymer parts below their melting point. Nonetheless, the efficiency of the weld was poor below 100 J/m^2 without any apparent defects such as porosity, Figure 4.

Figure 4: mode I fracture energy release rate (G_{IC} in J/m^2) versus penetration time for PEEK in the oven under argon atmosphere at 330°C, 340°C and 348°C

In this temperature range, there is a competition between crystallization and melting. Differential Scanning Calorimeter thermograms were performed on the samples that were held at 340°C for 6, 63 and 1000 hours, Figure 5. They show that a reorganization of the spherulites occurs with longer times. When the time increases, the melting point is higher and the melting peak is narrower; thus the spherulites should be bigger and with a better size distribution. In this temperature range, the mobility of the polymer chains is reduced and only parts of the chains can participate in the adhesion interpenetration phenomenon, while other parts stay embedded in crystalline regions. For samples welded at 348°C, an adhesion energy saturation was reached around 100 J/m^2 . The temperature of the melting process is spread over several decades. We may assume that the saturation of the adhesion energy corresponds to the free chain ends that were too short to form mechanically effective links. In the same oven, above the melting temperature, the interface was fully healed, all chains could contribute by destruction of the majority of the spherulites and penetration into the opposite side of the interface to a few N_e (monomers number between entanglements) distance [24] and co-crystallize on both sides of the interface.

Figure 5: DSC thermograms for specimens maintained at 340°C for 6h, 63h and 1000h

Short time weldings were possible with the new experimental device. The weld efficiency of 1 mm PEEK parts increased with increasing the infrared source holding time, Figure 6. The preheating temperature was 250°C. The arrows in the figure indicate cases where the crack did not propagate at the interface, which means that the bulk fracture energy was reached.

Figure 6: Mode I fracture energy release rate (G_{IC} in J/m^2) for PEEK versus infrared source holding time for a preheating temperature of 250°C.

Figure 7 shows the evolution of the relative mode I fracture energy release rate for PEEK carbon fiber reinforced composites (APC2) versus infrared source holding time for two different thicknesses. Increasing the preheating temperature from 250°C to 290°C has a beneficial effect on the measured fracture energy. For the 140 μm thick sample, a very small fracture energy could be measured with a preheating temperature of 250°C. In this case, increasing the IR source holding time has no effect on adhesion because the sample surface temperature is stabilized. For a preheating temperature of 290°C, the fracture energy increases slightly with the IR source holding time but is always less than half of the fully healed sample. The response of the 280 μm thick sample is totally different. Whereas, the fracture energy appears to be maximum for a preheating temperature of 290°C even at short IR source holding times, important increases were observed for a preheating temperature of 250°C. Indeed, for an IR source holding time of 3.5s, the adhesion phenomenon starts to appear and for an IR source holding time of 6.5s, the interface energy is close to the optimum. We have to be careful analyzing

Figure 7 because the sample thickness has only an indirect influence on the measured energy release rate, by changing the thermal properties of the sample and notably the temperature of the surface brought into contact. Thus, we need to do thermal modeling to obtain a deeper understanding of the phenomenon.

Figure 7: Relative mode I critical strain energy release rate for APC2 versus infrared source holding time for a preheating temperature of 250°C and 290°C for different sample thickness (a) 140 μm (b) 280 μm thick sample, $G_{IC\infty}$ is the value for a totally healed sample

Thermal modeling

Temperature profiles could only be obtained by modeling because studied times and volumes are very small. During the welding process, the sample surface temperature increases with the presence of the infrared source, from the mount preheating temperature to a maximum temperature, Figure 8. Upon withdrawal of the source, the temperature decreases quickly. After pressure is applied, both surfaces come in contact and the interdiffusion process starts at the interface. We first assume a radiation boundary condition at sample surface when the infrared source is in front the sample. A very small convection flux was also taken into account. Then when the parts are in contact, interface flux is assumed to be zero since the problem is symmetric. The opposite side flux is controlled by adhesive thermal resistance during the welding process, which increases when pressure is applied.

Figure 8: Surface and Interface temperature modeling of APC2 sample with a thickness of 280 μm

Holding the infrared source longer changed the material surface thermal history by increasing the maximum attained temperature. Consequently, interface cooling curve is modified and the temperature is higher when contact occurs and interdiffusion phenomenon is longer, as shown in Figure 9 in the APC2 case. Note that adhesion energy should not be considered directly proportional to a simple integration of interface cooling curves, as chain mobility varies strongly with temperature. Rheological measurements are a good way to evaluate this dependence through an average reptation time. It would be interesting to use the interface cooling curve to determine the evolution of the connecting chain density, i.e. density of chains that penetrate the opposite side to a sufficient distance to make a strong link.

Figure 9: Sample interface cooling curves for different infrared source holding times, for APC2, thickness 280 μm .

This notion seems more appropriate for characterizing adhesion than considering the interpenetration distance of polymer segments [14]. Qualitatively, the connecting chain density increases when the contact temperature increases. We assume that the interpenetration is not efficient below a temperature T_s . It is important to remember that we are working with a polydisperse product, which means that different chain lengths are present. Below T_s , chain motion is reduced and chains do not contribute to adhesion by creating efficient bridges across the interface, as discussed previously. An important phenomenon that reduces chain mobility is the appearance of crystallinity as some chains are embedded in spherulites. T_s was determined by delaying the application of contact and is valid for a given cooling curve. In the case of PEEK with 5.5s IR holding time, adhesion between the two parts was negligible for a 15s delay of pressure application, which corresponds to a contact temperature of 290°C. Two main parameters having a direct effect on interdiffusion appear to be modified when increasing the IR holding time, nevertheless it appears that the contact temperature is more important than interdiffusion duration. Indeed, after 5.5 s IR holding time and with a 250°C preheating temperature, PEEK samples were brought into contact and pressure was applied for only 0.25s. The welded sample was directly ejected and quenched in water which stopped interdiffusion and crystallization phenomena. This sample was fully healed, because the crack did not propagate at the interface. Such a short contact time was sufficient for chains to interdiffuse and to reach an optimal connecting chain density.

Composite fracture surface

Composite fracture surfaces after the wedge test were analyzed using a scanning electronic microscope (SEM), Figure 10. Samples with very different measured mode I critical strain energy release rate G_{IC}

were selected. We can observe very different fracture surfaces. In the case with a low G_{IC} , a few surface modifications can be seen. PEEK matrix fusion should have appeared very locally. In the opposite case with a high G_{IC} , the fracture mode is ductile as we can observe zones where the matrix was pulled. Moreover, we mainly observed bare fibers; the interface between fiber and matrix was broken.

(a) (b)
Figure 10: APC2 fracture surface for samples with
(a) small measured energy release rate, (b) high measured energy release rate

CONCLUSIONS

Continuous processing such as thermoplastic automated tow placement is controlled by local matrix fusion. This is related to the interdiffusion process, where chains interpenetrate both sides of the interface creating bridges that transmit stress if there are some entanglements. A new experimental device was developed to weld PEEK and PEEK carbon fiber composite samples under controlled conditions and short times. The influence of the processing parameters on the interdiffusion process was qualitatively highlighted, measuring the mode I critical strain release energy rate with the wedge double cantilever beam test. Based on thermal modeling of the process and especially the interface temperature, outlines have been given to evaluate the importance of parameters for the welding such as maximum attained temperature, contact temperature and interdiffusion phenomenon duration. Interdiffusion is perturbed at the low end of the interface cooling curve by crystallization which could enhance adhesion by other microscopic mechanisms; its influence on adhesion should be better understood. The presented results combined with complementary experiments that would give the temperature dependence of chain diffusion, would predict the quality of the weld for PEEK and PEEK carbon fiber reinforced composites from processing conditions. This is a key step in optimizing the quality of manufactured components and in encouraging widespread composite continuous process use.

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